

Kaniadakis Entropy and its Link to a Quadratic Equation with $b=kx$

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Kaniadakis entropy is a power law entropy - $\sum_i p_i^k (p_i^k - p_i^{-k}) / 2k$ which yields Shannon's entropy in the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit. Tsallis entropy is another power law entropy which also yields the Shannon result for $q \rightarrow 1$. Thus, Kaniadakis entropy must have other distinguishing features. We have already argued in previous notes that it uses p instead of p^q (Tsallis) case for averaging and that $p^q dF/dp = 1$ cannot be used to find $F(p) = -ei/T$, where $F = \ln k(p)$.

In the literature, it is well known that $\exp_k(ei/T) \exp_k(-ei/T) = 1$ ((1)) and that $\ln k(p, k) = \ln k(p, -k)$ ((2)). In fact, one may obtain the Kaniadakis function from even/odd function considerations from ((1)) alone and put this function to the power $1/k$. (If $0 < k < 1$, then for $k = 1/3$, this is like an AND probability 3 times.)

It turns out, however, that such a result is linked to the solution of a quadratic equation (for $b = -kx$) for which $(-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}) * (b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}) / (4aa)$ yields 1 automatically if $c = -a$. This, in turn, is linked with a form: $B - 1/B = kx$. If B is taken to power k and $1/B$ to power k and one divides by $2k$, then ((2)) holds. Thus, the properties of Kaniadakis entropy and $\exp_k(ei/T)$ are strongly linked with a quadratic solution for which $b = kx$, i.e. is odd in energy. In other words, there seems to be a deterministic quadratic equation for which the sum of B^k and $B^k(ei/T)$ is a constant.

Kaniadakis Solution Based Solely on $\exp_k(ei) \exp_k(-ei) = 1$

Here we consider obtaining the Kaniadakis $\exp_k(ei)$ simply from a consideration of $\exp_k(ei) \exp_k(-ie) = 1$ assuming that:

$$\exp_k(x)^k = f_{\text{even}}(x) + f_{\text{odd}}(x) \quad \text{where } x = -ei/T \quad ((3))$$

Then: $1 = \{f_{\text{even}}(x) + f_{\text{odd}}(x)\} \{f_{\text{even}}(x) - f_{\text{odd}}(x)\}$ or for the simple case of $f_{\text{odd}}(x) = kx$

$$\exp_k(x) = \{ \sqrt{1 + k^2 x^2} + kx \}^{1/k} \quad ((4))$$

Thus, at first it may seem that the condition $\exp_k(x) \exp_k(-x) = 1$ is key, but really ((4)) is the solution of a quadratic with $b = -kx$ and this implies one automatically gains the extra features.

$$aB^k - B^k x + c = 0 \quad \text{from } aB + c/B = kx \quad ((5a)) \quad a = 1/2, c = -1/2$$

$$B = kx + \sqrt{k^2 x^2 + 1} \quad ((5b))$$

Here the + solution is taken so probability is positive.

One may then take $B^{1/k}$ (and then divide by $2k$) to obtain $\exp_k(x)$. This is like an AND probability for $k = 1/n$ etc.

The form ((5a)) may be written as:

$$.5 (B - 1/B) = kx \quad ((5c)) \text{ showing how } \ln k(x) \text{ appears.}$$

In other words, the quadratic solution, with $b=-kx$, is the basis of both $\exp k(ei)\exp k(-ei) = 1$ and the $\{ p \text{ power } k - p \text{ power } -k \} / 2k$ form.

As a result, it may be possible to find the quadratic equation ((5a)) in nature such that $B \text{ power } 1/k$ represents a Kaniadakis distribution. If $0 < k < 1$, then a value of $k=1/2$ means $1/k = 2$ etc and so taking the power $1/k$ is simply an AND probability statement (and then dividing by $2k$). Thus, B , the solution of ((5a)), may be considered to be a probability. In such a case, Bkx is probability *fraction* $(-ei/T)$ and this is somehow connected to a constant $-1/2$ and probability squared: $-1/2$ probability * probability.

Alternatively, k may be looked upon as a kind of fixed probability augmented by the factor ei/T such that BB differs from the product by a fixed constant c .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that two well known Kaniadakis entropy properties: $\ln k(p) = 1/2k * (p \text{ power } k - p \text{ power } -k)$ and $\exp k(x)\exp k(-x)=1$ both follow from a solution of the quadratic equation: $.5 BB - Bkx - .5=0$. Here $x= -ei/T$ and k is a given fraction ($0 < k < 1$) The solution B then taken to the power $1/k$ (and then divided by $2k$) yields the Kaniadakis $\exp k(-ei/T)$. Here k is a fraction, so if one has $1/3$, then $1/k$ is 3 or one has an AND probability. In other words, B is a base probability (like the probability that a seed does not get eaten by a bird in a day while it takes three days for the seed to germinate). The quadratic equation represents a physical constraint on a product of the base probability and its link to a constant and a fraction k multiplied by the probability and (ei/T) which is like an average of partial energy or a fixed probability enhanced by ei/T and multiplied by B . In other words, using the quadratic equation suggests that B is computed in a somewhat deterministic manner.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. Non Linear Kinetics Underlying Generalized Statistics (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/0103467>